

AI-PRISM

D4.1 – AI-PRISM Human Robot Cooperation Ambient (I)

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
WP	Work Package
T	Task
AI	Artificial intelligence
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development/Deployment
2D/3D/6D	Two/three/six Dimensions

The AI-PRISM project

AI-PRISM will provide industrial users with **human-centred artificial intelligence (AI)-based solutions to create a more efficient, resilient, digital, sustainable and high-quality European manufacturing industry.**

To do so, we will develop an **integrated and scalable environment** with solutions adapted to dynamic and unpredictable manufacturing scenarios that require tasks that are difficult to automate and where speed and versatility are essential to meet users' needs. Furthermore, the solutions will be specific to semi-automated and collaborative manufacturing in flexible production processes and will not require specific robotic programming skills.

Our solutions ecosystem will have four main pillars:

1. **A human-centred collaborative robotic platform** oriented to ease hard-to-automate manufacturing tasks.
2. **A human-robot cooperative environment** powered by trustworthy AI.
3. **Social human-agent-robots teams' collaboration** — AI-based safety monitoring and robot control mechanisms to detect and avoid unsafe situations and ensure social and physical safety.
4. **An open-access network portal** to offer compliant infrastructure.

To evaluate our solutions' performance, transferability, scalability and large-scale deployment, we will perform demonstrations in real operating environments. Specifically, in **four user pilots involving key manufacturing sectors** — furniture, food/beverage, built-in appliances and electronics —, **types of robots and industrial processes that are difficult to automate, plus a generic demonstration facility.**

In addition to seeking quantitative improvements in the manufacturing sector, **AI-PRISM aims to use technological innovation to support a paradigm shift in which AI, robotics and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are integrated into the manufacturing domain for the improvement of flexible production processes**, becoming a viable and widespread alternative for European factories.

During the next three years, **25 partners** from **12 countries** will join forces to make AI-PRISM a reality. From educational institutions to research and technology organisations, robot manufacturers, industries and use case providers; our interdisciplinary consortium brings together all the actors of the human-robot collaboration value chain and involves key experts in SSH, standardisation, exploitation, and dissemination.

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1. Introduction

1.1. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

Deliverable describes consecutive releases of the CI/CD framework (code repositories, CI/CD pipelines and project scaffolds to support the development, integration, and validation of AI-based modules). Software releases of libraries of AI-based modules to enhance perception and reasoning capabilities of agents in the collaborative ambient, as well as to enable ambient level coordination and learning tasks by human demonstration.

The main objective of WP4 is to enhance the perception and reasoning capabilities of robotic agents using AI based modules. This work package also provides continuous integration / continuous development (CI/CD) pipelines and infrastructure to support development, integration, and validation of AI based solutions in AI-PRISM. The following specific objectives are targeted in WP4:

- Design and validation of continuous integration and validation pipelines for AI-PRISM AI-based solutions.
- Design and development of AI-based perception modules to enhance perception capabilities in the ambient.
- Design and development of AI-based reasoning modules to enhance the reasoning capabilities of individual agents in the collaborative ambient.
- Design and development of AI-based reasoning modules to coordinate activities of groups of agents in the collaborative ambient.
- Develop programming by demonstration methods to transfer knowledge from humans to robots.

1.2. STATUS GUIDELINES

Status	Description
Planned	Task defined and assigned to an Epic
In progress	Task under current development
Ready to test	Task developed and ready to be tested
Completed	Task finished and tested

On hold	Task temporary paused
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2. Architecture of AI-enhancing tools

All modules below are developed as part of WP4 – AI enhancing tools.

Reference architecture is available

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/reference-architecture.git>

3. Modules

3.1. CI/CD FRAMEWORK FOR AI-BASED SOLUTIONS – CD (PIAP)

The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery>

3.1.1. GITLAB TOOLING

Module name		GITLAB TOOLING		
General description		Gitlab tooling is the basis for our CI/CD. The infrastructure is located on independent servers at PIAP. It enables, among others: tracking tasks in the project, code repository, CI/CD pipelines and package and containers registry.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional gitlab instance. It includes code repository and basic project templates.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First gitlab instance • First templates 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tooling. It includes issue tracking and	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduced issue tracking • First CI pipeline integration (frontend_template project) 	Completed

		container registry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added default CI/CD runner • Enabled container registry • Gitlab updates • Extended storage space (>1TB) 	
3.0	TBD	Third tooling version. It includes more templating features and new component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD • Generate helm templates for each componet 	Planned

3.1.2. FRONTEND TEMPLATE

Module name		FRONTEND TEMPLATE		
General description		Frontend template based on the project identity colours and theme with examples pages including useful components for the rest of project partners. It also provides general guidelines on how to use it and best practices.		
Gitlab link		NextJS frontend template available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first functional frontend template for the project with NextJS framework. It includes the project colours and some basic components in different pages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First NextJS version with generic components • Integration of project theme and styles • First Dockerfile 	Completed
2.0	December 31 st 2023	This is the epic of the second version of the template. It	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New components added. 	Partially completed. ON-HOLD:

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		includes an update of the look and feel of the template to bring it closer to the theme of the project, including specific components that partners will need. A first integration with Keycloak will be made for the login and jinja templating features will be added.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring the template closer to the theme of the project. • First integration with Keycloak login (different branch). • Continuous integration added. • Minor bugs fixed. • Jinja templating features delayed to next epic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keycloak integration <p>Delayed to next epic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating ON-HOLD
3.0	March 31 st 2024	Third frontend version. It includes Jinja templating features and new status component.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating features delayed from the previous epic. • Status management component. • Graph component. • Solved issues raised from partners. 	<p>Partially completed.</p> <p>IN PROCESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jinja templating

3.1.3. CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS

Module name		CLUSTER MANAGEMENT TOOLS		
General description		Cluster Management is a platform, based on Rancher as software, for the centralised management of multiple Kubernetes clusters.		
Gitlab link		Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/cluster_management		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status

1.0	-	This is the first version in which Rancher on Kubernetes is installed and configured manually on Kubernetes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software pre-installation: Docker, K3s and Helm. • Installation of Rancher on Kubernetes cluster. 	Completed
2.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the second version. It includes the integration of installing all software into a shell script, along with the necessary configuration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service verification and installation automation. • Modifying the Kubernetes node for SSL certificate configuration. • Adding a new cluster of AI-PRISM CMT for application deployment. • Application catalogue in Rancher. • DNS deployment fixed with an alternative (cigip-dev branch). 	Partially completed. ON-HOLD: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ssl certificates

3.1.4. MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES

Module name	MACHINE LEARNING TEMPLATES
General description	Machine learning templates for easy integration.
Gitlab link	Cluster Management available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/continuous-delivery/ml-project-template
Released versions	

Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	-	This is the first version on templates	First generic ML template	In progress
2.0	June – July 2024			

3.2. AI-BASED PERCEPTION ENHANCING MODULES – PE (FBK)

The GitLab software repository is available here: <https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules>.

3.2.1. OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION (2D/3D)

Module name		OBJECT AND DEFECT DETECTION		
General description		Object and defect detection module is designed to work in, among others: in the VIGO pilot, it detects objects and their positioning, as well as detects defects in the semiconductor structure.		
Gitlab link		Gitlab is available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ai-based-perception-modules/object-and-defect-detection		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31 st 2024	This is the first prototype of module	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detects key points on the structure • Annotation tool implemented 	Completed
2.0	June-July 2024	This is the epic of the second version of the tool. Some improvements of existing features.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add CI/CD tools for containerisation • Add defects detection 	Planned
3.0	TBD	Third tooling version.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add Helm-charts to catalogue via CI/CD 	PLANNED

3.2.2. OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION

Module name		OBJECT 6D POSE ESTIMATION		
General description		This module performs model-based zero-shot object 6D pose estimation, determining the rotation and translation of an object within a scene. It takes as input the 3D point cloud representing the object and an RGBD image capturing the scene containing that object and produces as output the object’s rotation and translation transformations relative to a global reference frame.		
Gitlab link		The Git repository is available here: https://github.com/andreacaraffa/aiprism-sensing . For now, the access to the repository is set to private. We will release the code publicly by the end of the project.		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	March 31, 2024	First version of the code performing object 6D pose estimation without the need for task-specific training data	Python implementation based on the PyTorch library	Completed
2.0	June 2024	Second version of the code containing also a ROS2 wrapper of the python code released in v1 and a Gazebo simulator	Module demonstrator running in a controlled Lab environment containing a collaborative robotic arm spray painting a chair	In progress
3.0	TBD	Final version of the code.	Module demonstrator running in the AndreuWorld pilot facility	Planned

3.3. AI-BASED AGENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES – DR (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/agent-level-reasoning-acting-and-control>

3.3.1. COORDINATION OF AGENTS

Module name		Coordination of agents		
General description		This module will coordinate the different agents that play a role in the execution of tasks (e.g. control, vision, planning, etc).		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of march 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	A finite state machine that coordinates the application. For the insertion of the PBC, it checks for the insertion states before executing the next phase so that the insertion becomes robust (e.g. first make contact with the corner, then one of the sides, etc).	Ready to test
2.0		Exploration of methodologies and available packages for coordination of agents in ROS2.	State machines such as YASMIN or SMACH are being explored as a replacement of the FSM used in Orocos (i.e. rFSM)	In progress
3.0		Selection of a coordination methodology	A state machine, behavioural tree, or pertinent will be	Planned

		based on the requirements of the application	selected. If it suffices, a state machine will be used	
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3.4. **AI-BASED AMBIENT LEVEL REASONING ENHANCING MODULES - CR (UPV)**

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning>

3.4.1. REASONING MODEL

Module name		REASONING MODEL		
General description		The AI-PRISM data model is a set of classes that define the elements and relationships needed to model a company industrial plant of any pilot or company.		
Gitlab link		AI-PRISM data model available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aiprism-reasoning-model		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	January 21 st 2024	This is the first version of the data model. It defines the main model structure and documentation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentation about the Data Model. • Definition Model tables. • Capability Model tables. • Schedule Model tables. 	Completed
2.0		This second version includes a first instance of the model based on AW use case.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition inserts • Schedule inserts 	Completed
3.0		The third version provides the possibility of importing data from an Excel files.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Node-Red flow to import and structure data. 	IN PROCESS

3.4.2. SCHEDULING MODULE

Module name		SCHEDULING MODULE		
General description		The AI-PRISM Scheduling model is a representation of all entities, their properties and the relation between them. This model allows the scheduling of the factory processes taking into consideration all available resources and restrictions, including cobots and its training requirements.		
Gitlab link		Available here: https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/ambient-reasoning/aw-scheduler		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	November 31 st 2023	Gather data necessity and data output from initial design and generate an initial data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initial data model for scheduling module input • Initial data model for scheduling module output 	Completed
2.0	March 2024	Generate a second iteration for da data model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated data model 	In progress
3.0	End of March 2024	Create a standardized version of the data model according to standard IEC62264	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized data model 	In progress

3.5. HUMAN - MACHINE INTERACTION (HMI) MODULES – HI (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

3.5.1. KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE

Module name	KINESTHETIC TEACHING INTERFACE
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General description		The module allows the users to interact with the robot by force interaction in cartesian space by an admittance controlled based on measured forces in the end effector. The module can be re-configured to allow changes in position, orientation, or both.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	The module allows the user to kinaesthetically guide the robot, without relying on the kinaesthetic functionalities provided by the robot manufacturer	Ready to test
2.0	TBD	Backend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Facilitates mode switching	In progress
3.0	TBD	Frontend integration to facilitate user re-configuration and execution	Allows the user to launch the kinaesthetic interaction from a GUI	Planned

3.6. PROGRAMMING BY DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT – PD (KUL)

Software available here:

<https://gitc.piap.lukasiewicz.gov.pl/ai-prism/wp4/human-robot-interaction>

3.6.1. DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT

Module name		DEMONSTRATION ENVIRONMENT		
General description		An environment to facilitate the acquisition of demonstrations, processing of the signals and finally using them to learn robot skills.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repositories: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller and https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/phd/cristian-vergara/u0108073/traPPCA_lib		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	Acquires demonstrations of some parts of the task and generated a learned model in a JSON format.	Ready to test
2.0	TBD	Backend integration for data acquisition, signal processing and learning of robot skills	Technological tools that facilitate the learning process and the configuration of it	In progress
3.0	TBD	Frontend integration to facilitate the acquisition of the data by non-expert users	Allows the user to configure and perform signal acquisition through a GUI	Planned
4.0	TBD	Frontend integration to facilitate the learning process by non-expert users	Allows the user to configure and generate a model through a GUI	Planned

3.6.2. EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT

Module name		EXECUTION ENVIRONMENT		
General description		An environment to execute the learned model based on constraint-based and sensor-based task specifications. It is based on the existing eTaSL framework developed at KUL.		
Gitlab link		For now available in internal private repository: https://gitlab.kuleuven.be/rob/projects/ai-prism/ai-prism-controller		
Released versions				
Version	Due date	Description	High-level features	Status
1.0	31 st of March 2024	Module suitable for preliminary demonstration on the applicability of the module for the KEBA pilot case	Executes learned skills for certain parts of the task (e.g. pick the pcb), and modeled skills for others (e.g. robust force-based insertion)	Ready to test
2.0	TBD	Integrate the Orocos-based existing component with ROS2	Done by bridging Orocos and ROS2	Ready to test
3.0	TBD	Development of a ROS2 node that is independent of Orocos and can be used to execute eTaSL skills.	This is exploratory work that we are doing in order to integrate better with the rest of the partners, and facilitate the installation and execution according to the architecture of AI-Prism	In progress

4. Conclusions

4.1.1. SUMMARY

The report describes the software versions and their status in a tabular manner.

4.1.2. NEXT STEPS

The next versions of deliverable will contain descriptions of subsequent versions of the software and new ones if they have not been created yet.